

An Analytical Study of The State of Academic Research on Islamic Economics and Islamic Banks in The United Arab Emirates Between the Years 1987 Until 2019

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 22, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: November 23, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Academic Research, Economics, Islamic Banks, Islamic financial</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7351940</p>	<p><i>The present study aims to analyze the studies which addressed the topics of Islamic economics and Islamic banks in the United Arab Emirates between the years 1987-2019. To achieve this, aim the qualitative analytical methodology was utilized, and the analysis sample consisted of (360) studies which included university dissertations, books and studies published in refereed academic journals as well as papers submitted in academic conferences. The study concluded that the topics which delved into Islamic economics and Islamic banking during the period of study in the Emirates are: financial transactions in Muslim jurisprudence: 34.8%, Islamic financial institutions and banks 28.9%, planning and Islamic policies: 11.9%, public finance and the Islamic financial system: 8%, international economy and Islamic economic relations: 6.9%, Islamic thought and international economic history: 5.5%, and Islamic economic development: 4%. The study showed that the higher ratio of the numbers of studies and university dissertations and books was between the years 2010-2019; in view of the official interest in Islamic economics in the United Arab Emirates during this period.</i></p>

Introduction

The academic and intellectual arena in the field of Islamic economics and banking in the UAE is in need of analytical study particularly given the lack of previous studies in this domain, where the author could not find scholars that previously tackled this topic in the UAE with the exception of one study which analyzed the academic output in Islamic economics and banking in Jordan, namely the study of Kamal Tawfiq Hattab titled: Manual of the Authors in Islamic Economics and Banking in Jordan, which was published by the International Institute of Islamic Thought in 2013., and the author benefited from the said study.

Study Problem, Significance and Questions

The study problem is confined to the lack of a previous analytical study which focuses on what was produced in books and studies in refereed academic journals and papers presented at conferences and university dissertations on Islamic economics and banks in the UAE; which does not allow for the achievement of scientific accumulation in addition to repetition of some topics, as well as not focusing on the volume of academic production in this field in the UAE.

The significance of this study lies in endeavoring to fill the above-mentioned gap in the service of Islamic economics and drawing a map for research in this specialization, in addition to being an analytical presentation of the academic studies published in refereed academic journals and papers submitted at academic conferences, university dissertations and published books in the United Arab Emirates.

The study seeks to answer the following two questions:

First question: what are the topics tackled in the field of Islamic economics and banking during the period of study in the UAE?

Second question: what are the numbers of papers, dissertations and books authored during the period subject of the study? And what are the rates of growth?

Methodology and Boundaries of the Study

The study relies on the analytical descriptive method and the content analysis method for studies that treated the topics of Islamic economics and banks in the UAE in the period (1987-2019), and the start of the study was identified as the year 1987, given that the author did not tackle any research output on the subject of the study prior to that year, and the results of this study are based on what was accessed in books, university dissertations and refereed studies in Islamic economics and banking whether those studies were published in academic journals or were papers in academic conferences held in the UAE during the period which is the subject of the study. On the other hand, in view of differences between the specialists on the nature of the topics and studies

associated with Islamic economics, or that do not belong to it, the present study attempts to elucidate the subjects which combine economics, banks and Islamic Fiqh (jurisprudence) to the extent possible.

Study procedures:

The author examined the titles of studies in academic journals and the titles of conferences and university dissertations, and communication was undertaken with the quarters that published those studies, in order to obtain the academic materials and their abstracts. Actually, the author looked at 360 academic studies.

Statistical Analysis of Academic Materials

The present study included 360 academic studies distributed across four sections, namely:

First section: Academic studies published in refereed academic journals

The number of refereed academic studies were 100 studies issued by 5 refereed academic journals as is shown in Table (1):

Table 1. Numbers of studies published in refereed academic journals

Journals' Names	Number of Studies	Percentage
Journal of Sharia & Law, United Arab Emirates University	37	%37
University of Sharjah Journal of Sharia and Law Sciences	31	%31
College of Islamic and Arabic Studies Journal/ Dubai	18	%18
University of Sharjah Journal for Humanities & Social Sciences	9	%9
Al-Mi'yār Journal / Imam Malik College for Islamic Sharia and Law	5	%5
Total:	100	%100

At the forefront is the Journal of Sharia & Law, the United Arab Emirates University, followed by University of Sharjah Journal of Sharia and Law Sciences, and then comes the College of Islamic and Arabic Studies Journal/ Dubai in third position, followed by University of Sharjah Journal for Humanities & Social Sciences in fourth position, and in last position is Al-Mi'yār Journal / Imam Malik College for Islamic Sharia and Law. The author attributes the causes of difference to the fact that the Journal of Sharia & Law issued by the Faculty of Law in the United Arab Emirates University is the first university to be established in the UAE, where it was founded in 1976 A.D., and the first issue of the Journal was issued in May 1987, while the University of Sharjah was established in 1997, but it founded a faculty for Shari'ah (Islamic Law) contrary to what is the case now in the United Arab Emirates University which lacks a faculty of Shari'ah. This produced a situation where there is a large number of teaching staff in the field of Muslim jurisprudence in the University of Sharjah and a small number in the United Arab Emirates University. Thus the number of studies was close between the two universities despite the distance between the dates of their establishment. As to the low number in the College of Islamic and Arabic Studies Journal and Al-Mi'yār Journal issued by the Imam Malik College for Islamic Sharia and Law in Dubai, the author attributes the dearth of publishing in those two journals to an academic cause, namely that some Arab universities such as the University of Jordan, for instance, do not recognize these two journals for purposes of publishing academic studies.

Section two: Papers submitted at academic conferences.

The number of papers submitted at academic conferences amounted to 229 papers, submitted at 8 academic conferences as is shown in Table 2:

Table 2. Numbers of papers submitted at academic conferences

Conference	Year	Number of Studies
The 14 th Annual Islamic Banking and Finance Conference	2005	46
The Conference of Islamic Banking Between Reality and Expectations	2009	41
Islamic Economics Conference: Need for Implementation And The Imperatives Of Transformation For Islamic Economics	2015	14
Islamic Economic Fiqh Forum	2015	48
Islamic Economic Fiqh Forum	2016	17
Islamic Economic Fiqh Forum	2017	35

Conference Towards Development of the Economic Reality in the Shadow of the Theory of Islamic Economics	2017	9
The Virtual Currencies Conference in the Balance	2019	18
Total		228

Expression of interest in presenting the topics of Islamic economics in academic conference began at the outset of this millennium, and it is the view of the author that the abundance of conferences began actually after His Highness Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum launched the initiative of Dubai: The Capital of Islamic Economy initiative in the year 2013 A.D., whereby those conferences emerged to actualize this initiative.

Section Three: Books published by Emirati institutions and publishing houses

The number of books during the period subject of the study amounted to 5 published books, four of which were issued by a single publishing house, and one book where the publishing house is anonymous as is shown in Table 3:

Table 3. Emirati institutions and publishing houses

Names of the institutions and publishing houses	Number of books
University Book House - Al Ain	4
Unidentified publisher	1

It is worthy of mention that the ratio of publication in the area of books is weak compared to other areas, and the researcher may attribute this to the dearth of Emirati publishing houses specialized in Islamic economics in particular and the field of Islamic studies in general, in addition to the predominance of electronic books issued by publishing houses outside the Emirates over the Emirati publishing market.

Section Four: Academic dissertations and theses issued by Emirati colleges and universities

The number of theses and dissertations during the period subject of the study is 27, both Master's and doctoral dissertations, issued by the University of Sharjah and the College of Islamic and Arabic Studies Journal/ Dubai, as is shown in Table 4

Table 4. Number of University theses and dissertations

Names of the Universities	Number of Theses
Sharjah University	20
College of Islamic and Arabic Studies Dubai in Dubai	7
Total:	27

Based on an inductive reading of the previous tables it may be observed that the number of theses is not large in general compared to the number of academic studies whether printed in refereed academic journals or submitted at conferences. A researcher may attribute this to the fact that graduate studies in the United Arab Emirates University are relatively recent, where Emirati universities began to offer graduate (higher studies) in the field of Islamic studies after the year 2000 A.D., where the first university thesis that the author examined in the field of Islamic economics was in 2005 at the College of Islamic and Arabic Studies in Dubai –currently Al Wasl University-. Indeed, the author discerned palpable enthusiasm for graduate studies in the field of Islamic studies in general and Islamic economics in particular through a succession of years as is shown in Table 5:

Table 5. Distribution of university theses over the years

	University of Sharjah	College of Islamic and Arabic Studies		University of Sharjah	College of Islamic and Arabic Studies
2005	0	1	2012	1	0
2006	0	0	2013	1	2
2007	0	0	2014	1	1
2008	0	0	2015	3	0
2009	1	2	2016	3	1
2010	0	0	2017	3	0

2011	1	0	2018	6	0
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On the other hand, there is a strong inclination to expand graduate studies in the field of jurisprudential and economic studies in Emirati universities, where, for instance, Hamdan Bin Mohammed Smart University Dubai (HBMSU) which relies on smart education based on modern communication methods- offers a master's degree in Islamic banks and banking, and also Mohammed V University (Agdal) - Abu Dhabi offers a master's program in Maliki jurisprudence and contemporary issues, and a doctoral program in Islamic Law and the issues of contemporary society, and, moreover, the Imam Malik College for Islamic Sharia and Law offers a Master's program in Islamic Jurisprudence and its Foundations.

Response to the questions of the study

Response to the first question: what are the topics studied in Islamic economics and banking during the period of the study in the Emirates?

It would be possible to confine the topics to the following: jurisprudence of financial transactions, Islamic financial institutions and banks, Islamic planning and economic policies, public finance and Islamic financial system, international economy and Islamic economic relations, Islamic thought and economic history, Islamic economic development, and departing from these topics we find that the academic materials which were investigated in the present study are distributed across the topics as shown in Table 6:

Table 6. Titles of Subjects

Subject	University dissertations	Scientific Journals	Scientific Conferences papers	Books	Total	Percentage
Jurisprudence of financial transactions	18	50	56	1	125	%34.8
Islamic banks and financial institutions	4	25	74	1	104	%28.9
Islamic economic planning and policies	2	3	36	2	43	%11.9
Public finance and an Islamic financial system	2	12	15	0	29	%8
International economy and Islamic economic relations	1	3	20	1	25	%6.9
Islamic economic thought and history	0	7	13	0	20	%5.5
Islamic economic development	0	0	14	0	14	%4
Total	27	100	228	5	360	%100

Based on an inductive reading of the contents of table number (VI) we can observe the following:

The topic of the jurisprudence of financial transactions occupied first position in view of its intimate connection to Islamic banking, in addition to the plethora of new developments in Islamic financial transactions leading to an abundance of research output, particularly since most of the modern financial developments require jurisprudential research coupled with attempts to generate religious rules. This was followed by the topic of Islamic banks and institutions in second position, in view of the growing interest of the UAE in Islamic economics particularly with the launching of the "Dubai: The Capital of Islamic Economy" initiative" not to mention the global interest in this specialization in the latter years; as to the third position it was associated with the topic of economic planning and Islamic economic policies which is an important subject particularly in the wake of the transformations which have engulfed the Arab region, which demanded transformations in planning and economic policies in a manner consistent with the needs and demands of Arab societies..

The topic of public finance and the Islamic financial system comes in fourth position and is something of great importance in contemporary reality, and requires an increase in the number of studies and research on it, and then comes the topic of international economics and Islamic economic relations in fifth position, and this is perhaps due to the fact that this type of studies requires being well versed in other languages in order to study and analyze the international economic conditions. The sixth position was occupied by the topic of Islamic economic thought and Islamic economic history. Undoubtedly, it would be impossible to understand and analyze the contemporary economic problems without understanding and analyzing economic history, and the evolution of economic thought related to these problems; which is something that necessitates increased interest in this topic to better analyze and understand the economic reality and the contemporary international economic changes. As to the final position it was occupied by the topic of Islamic economic development, and perhaps

this is due to the belief of the scholars that it would be difficult to change the economic situation in Arab countries.

The response to the second question: what is the number of studies, dissertations and books which were authored during the period subject of the study? And what are the rates of increase?

It would be possible for the researcher to distribute the academic materials in Islamic economics in the United Arab Emirates according to the segments of the following years, as is shown in Table 7:

Table 7. Distribution of Academic Materials based on Years

	1987-1989	1990-1999	2000-2009	2010-2019	Total
Scientific Conferences	0	0	87	141	228
	%0	%0	%38.2	%61.8	%63.3
Scientific Research	4	10	25	61	100
	%4	%10	%25	%61	%27.8
University theses	0	0	4	23	27
	%0	%0	%14.8	%85.2	%7.5
Books	0	0	1	4	5
	%0	%0	%20	%80	%1.4
Total	4	10	117	229	360
	%1.1	%2.8	%32.5	%63.6	%100

It would be possible to explain the accelerating rates of increase in publications through the following points:

- An increase in the intensity and severity of the economic problems from which humanity is suffering, and the failure of the traditional economic systems to alleviate the severity of these problems. Moreover, there is a worsening of the economic problems in the wake of the global financial crisis in particular, and what followed in great interest in Islamic economics and finance.
- Rising spread of Islamic banks, and the resultant emergence of Islamic financial products, and Islamic investment banking instruments, which has generated considerable interest among the researchers to become involved in these research topics, and to enrich the theoretical literature related to them.
- The adverse economic conditions that the Islamic states are suffering from in general, and what the Islamic banks represent in terms of promising environments that are replete with business opportunities.
- Increasing jurisprudential questioning by many scholars of the jurisprudential foundations upon which Islamic banks are based, and the resultant inclination to undertake jurisprudential and scientific scrutiny on this subject. (Hattab, 2013, p.30)
- The launching by His Highness Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum of the initiative of Dubai: The Capital of Islamic Economy initiative in 2013, and what followed in local interest in this topic represented in a plethora of academic conferences focusing on this topic.

Recommendations

Among the most prominent recommendations that may be addressed to the scholars and researchers and those in positions of responsibility at the centers of research and sections of Islamic economics in universities are the following:

- The imperative of directing research efforts and plans to the topics of economic development and planning and international economic relations, particularly in the shadow of the transformations witnessed in the Arab region.
- The necessity of distance from the jurisprudential peripheral matters which were previously addressed, whilst focusing on new developments in Fiqh (jurisprudence) and the issues associated with contemporary transactions.
- The necessity of directing efforts towards creating a generation of economists who combine the capability in Islamic studies and economic analysis.

Sources

Hattab, Kamal Tawfiq, (2013), Guide of Researchers in Islamic Economics and Banks in Jordan, 1st. ed., Herndon: International Institute of Islamic Thought.

Conflict of Interests:

The authors have nothing to disclose and have no commercial or financial interest in the products described in this paper.

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